

FEATURES OF THE RESULTS OF CLINICAL STUDIES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE

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Abstract. *It is important to suggest that in recent years, according to statistics, the incidence of chronic kidney disease among children and adults has been increasing worldwide, and the impact of this disease on the quality of life and social activity remains one of the pressing issues. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), when generalized, non-communicable diseases account for 74% of causes of death worldwide, with kidney disease ranking first among causes of death in 2019. Chronic kidney disease leads to severe consequences of non-communicable diseases, thus, reducing premature mortality from non-communicable diseases by a third by 2030 is included in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. Early diagnosis of chronic kidney disease, assessment of morphological changes occurring in the kidneys during the disease, development of effective treatment methods, prognosis and prevention of development of irreversible stages of chronic disease remain one of the urgent scientific problems.*

Keywords: *communicable disease, premature mortality, chronic kidney disease, transplantology, age division.*

Purpose of the study. To study the features of the results of clinical studies in patients with CKD.

Material and methods of the study. The scientific work was carried out at the Department of Medical Radiology of Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute (TashPMI) in the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Nephrology and Transplantology in 2019-2023. For solving the objectives, we examined 203 patients, including 151 patients (56 men and 95 women) with various stages of CKD aged 18 to 89 years and 52 practically healthy individuals (13 men and 39 women), who formed a comparison group aged 18 to 79 years. Age division was carried out according to the generally accepted scheme of periodization of biological age adopted in medicine and enshrined in WHO (issue No. 3 of 2017). Analysis of the age and gender of the adult contingent revealed that CKD prevailed in females - 63.0% (n = 95). Based on the results of the comprehensive examination, the patients of the main group were divided into four groups:

Group I consisted of 48 (31.8%) patients with CKD stages 1-2 (60-89 ml/min/1.73m²);

Group II consisted of 66 (43.7%) patients with CKD stage 3 (including stage 3A - 30 (45.4%), stage 3B - 36 (54.6%)) (30-59 ml/min/1.73m²);

Group III consisted of 37 (24.5%) with CKD stages 4-5 (including stage 4 - 20 (54.0%), 5 (ESRD) - (46.0%) (<15-29 ml/min/1.73m²);

Control group IV (n=52) consisted of practically healthy patients with normal SCF (> 90).

Results of the study. The analysis of clinical symptoms allowed us to determine the directions of therapeutic action and develop preventive approaches to timely and adequate treatment. The most interesting data are the analysis of clinical symptoms stage by stage, according to their formation. Thus, the analysis of the clinic from the initial stages of CKD allowed us to state that from the onset of the disease to the last stages, the patient is bothered by headaches and

edema syndrome, accounting for 49.6% and 44.3%, respectively. This is most likely due to the influence of arterial hypertension, which was detected in the majority of those examined (63.3%). Inspiratory dyspnea and the appearance of palpitations without cause and physical exertion were noted by 37 (24.5%) and 8 (5.2%) patients. It should be noted that from the initial stages, most patients experienced a feeling of thirst 47 (31.3%), as well as a number of dyspeptic disorders (35.7%). Among them, nausea and vomiting most often bothered patients, accounting for 23 (15.2%). At the same time, some patients had long-term anorexia 22 (14.5%). Patients with CKD are more often bothered by a slight increase in body temperature to subfebrile numbers in the evenings, which many do not pay attention to for many months and years. Such symptoms were detected in 22 (14.5%) patients.

However, as the underlying disease progresses, most patients develop a lot of complaints that are difficult to compare and isolate into one single disease. This circumstance causes some difficulties for the doctor, since many of these symptoms are temporary and may not always manifest clinically. Thus, most patients may occasionally experience dysuric symptoms, which are expressed in frequent urination, or sometimes lack of urine, burning and a feeling of heaviness in the urethra, which was detected in 19 (12.5%) patients. Often, such symptoms were accompanied by pain in the lumbar region and were noted by 53 studied participants (35.0%).

Certainly, the obtained data allow us to conclude that chronic kidney disease (CKD) is most often accompanied by arterial hypertension (66.2%), edema (44.3%) and may be accompanied by significant (21.1%), moderate (30.4%) or mild (31.1%) daily proteinuria. Cardiac (45.3%), dyspeptic (45.3%) and anemic (47.3%) syndromes may also occur. Headache is common (49.6%), while lumbar pain is less common (35.0%). A correlation was found between the frequency of clinical symptoms and an increase in the stage of CKD. With an increase in the stage of the disease with a progressive decrease in the glomerular filtration rate, clinical and laboratory symptoms of chronic diffuse damage manifest themselves in a more complex way. But at the same time, the edema syndrome is significantly less. The same symptoms were noticed by most contemporaries. Analysis of laboratory urine tests showed that in patients with different stages of CKD, developed on the basis of chronic diffuse glomerulonephritis, mainly, increased daily proteinuria prevails.

According to the gradations of NONR, significant A3, daily proteinuria was detected in 31.1% of patients. It wasn't found a certain relative pattern in the relationship with the stages of CKD and the degree of daily proteinuria. Significant proteinuria was detected in the group of patients with chronic diffuse glomerulonephritis nephrotic syndrome, moderate and mild in other patients.

The analysis of arterial hypertension severity revealed a relative relationship with the stage of CKD. With the increase in the stage of CKD, the frequency and severity of arterial hypertension increases. In this regard, cardiac complaints in patients, as well as anemic and dyspeptic disorders, increase. Arterial hypertension at the optimal stage is detected in 75.0% of patients, while at a severe stage - in 80.0%, and in terminal chronic renal failure (TCRF) it increases to 88.3% of cases. Cardiac complaints in the optimal stage of CKD are detected in 30%, dyspeptic disorders in 36%, anemic in 20%, in a severe stage, especially with TCRF, the above symptoms in 70.3%, 63.3%, 86.7% of cases, respectively.

The above-mentioned relative patterns are directly related to the pathogenetic conditions of development and progression of the dynamics of the course of chronic diffuse damage,

ultimately leading to profound disability and often to death. As it can be seen from the results of the analysis of the clinical picture and the main laboratory data, all symptoms of CKD begin gradually and increase as the disease progresses. By the final stages of the disease, patients present a number of complaints, the treatment of which individually and symptomatically seems to be a very difficult task. In this regard, we have tried to combine them into the main priority syndromes:

- Asthenoneurotic syndrome. It manifested itself as irritability, drowsiness, anxiety, decreased attention and memory, hearing loss, headache, dizziness, insomnia, occasional cramps in the muscles of the arms and legs, and decreased tendon reflexes. This syndrome was detected in 3 (1.9%) patients in Group I, in 41 (17.1%) patients in Group II, and in 27 (17.8%) patients in Group III.

- Cardiovascular syndrome. It manifested itself as shortness of breath, pain and heaviness in the heart, hypertension and related complaints, interruptions and heaviness in the heart, and tachycardia. Cardiovascular syndrome was detected in 22 (14.5%) patients in Group I, in 52 (34.4%) patients in Group II, and in 32 (21.1%) patients in Group III. In some patients, heart rhythm disturbances such as AV blocks and high-grade heart rhythm disturbances were registered in severe stages.

- Dyspeptic syndrome was manifested in 54 (35.7%) patients in the form of anorexia, dryness and bitterness in the mouth, nausea, taste perversion, diarrhea, a feeling of heaviness in the epigastrium and right hypochondrium.

- Bone and joint syndrome was registered in 12 (7.9%) patients out of the total number of patients and was manifested by pain in the bones, knee, interphalangeal joints, spine, which was explained by the progression of osteoporosis and hyperuricemia.

- Dystrophic syndrome was mainly observed in the late stages of the disease (in 5 (3.3%) patients of group 2, as well as in 8 (5.2%) of group 3 and was manifested by dry and itchy skin, weight loss and muscle atrophy.

- Hematological syndrome manifested itself in 34 (22.5%) patients starting from stage 3B of CKD in the form of Bright's anemia, thrombocytopenia, nosebleeds and gum bleeding.

- Edema syndrome was accompanied by hypertension and was registered in most patients (in 14 (9.2%) patients of group I, in 29 (19.2%) patients of group II, and in 32 (21.1%) patients of group III). Edemas often began with edema of the arms and legs and then gradually moved to the abdomen. Some patients had ascites.

It is particularly important to pay attention to the fact that some patients at stage C-3A experience pain in bones and joints, which is 3 (10.0%) patients. On the radiographs of the bones of these patients, elements of osteodystrophy, osteoid sutures, radiological signs of osteoclastic disorder and resorption of bones and joints of the arms and legs are observed. This circumstance is quite explainable by disorders of phosphorus-calcium metabolism in the body.

Certainly, analysis of the main clinical and laboratory symptoms and syndromes allowed us to highlight some aspects of the morbidity that doctors needed to pay attention to. First of all, we were concerned about patients with latent and hidden forms of the disease, whose symptoms were short-term or did not manifest themselves, but needed regular and thorough examination. Many of them suggested that intermittent headaches, puffiness of the hands and feet. In the background were patients with a gradual onset of the disease in the form of headaches, shortness of breath, edematous syndrome, which, in all likelihood, was associated with the development of

hypertension. Later, as the results showed, symptoms and syndromes of cardiovascular disorders were added, which progressed in each patient individually.

Moreover, special attention was required by patients who did not register any clinical symptoms of the disease up to stages C3-A, B. Most of these patients had minor proteinuria, detected only during medical examinations. Based on the main clinical and laboratory data, we distributed patients by clinical forms of the underlying disease. This distribution was no less important than the analysis of the clinical picture, since it allowed the doctor to focus on the treatment and prevention of all possible complications.

Analysis of anamnestic information allowed us to establish previously suffered chronic pyelonephritis in 44 (29.1%) patients, chronic glomerulonephritis in 21 (28.0%) patients, diabetic nephropathy in 24 (15.8%) patients, hypertension with kidney damage in 45 (29.8%) patients, and mixed forms of nephropathy were found in 17 (11.2%) patients. Analysis of clinical manifestations showed the prevalence of latent forms (31.2%), less frequently observed were edematous-hypertonic (20.0%), hematuric (18.0%), hypertensive (17.5%), nephrotic (13.3%) forms of the disease. Analysis of urinary syndrome showed that most of the examined patients had a tendency to increase leukocytes in the urine, which indicated the addition of bacterial flora.

Moreover, the increase in leukocytes occurred against the background of hyposthenuria. Further changes are characterized by proteinuria in varying quantities, and the higher the patient's protein loss, the more pronounced the clinical symptoms of the disease.

From a practical point of view, it is noteworthy that patients with latent forms of the disease have a decrease in the relative density of urine against the background of polyuria, and this condition can last for a long period. Almost all those examined later develop hypoisosthenuria and coarse urinary sediment in the form of microhematuria and hyaline casts. The parameters of the general urine analysis in all patients show that at the initial stage of CKD, polyuria is recorded, which the patient does not pay attention to for a long time and occurs with periods of exacerbation and absence. This circumstance indicates initial changes in the function of tubular reabsorption, with preserved function of the glomeruli of the kidneys and SCF.

However, at the stage of CKD C3-A, protein loss is already observed, albeit insignificant, but isosthenuria occurs and a decrease in relative density may indicate disturbances in the concentrating ability of the kidneys, disturbances in the reabsorption of water and minerals, and disturbances in the water-electrolyte balance.

All these pathological changes in turn can indirectly contribute to the occurrence of various complications and disorders in other organs and systems. In the general blood test indicators, we recorded a decrease in the hemoglobin level to 102.0 ± 2.5 g / l, and the number of red blood cells, averaging $4.1 \pm 0.3 \times 10^{12}$. With the aggravation of the severity of the disease in stages of CKD 3A and 3B with a significant decrease in SCF, a decrease in hemoglobin to 81.0 ± 2.0 g / l is noted, and the level of red blood cells averaged $3.3 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{12}$.

It is quite reasonable that the pathogenesis at this stage is intertwined with many symptoms and syndromes, which is characterized by a violation or absence of erythropoietin synthesis. This circumstance indicates a violation of the fibroblast function, as well as damage to the peritubular region of the kidneys with the juxtaglomerular apparatus of the nephron. In 4-5 stages of CKD, normochromic anemia with a decrease in hemoglobin and erythrocytes was stably recorded, amounting to 60.5 ± 2.2 g / l and 2.4 ± 0.5 g / l, respectively. Neutrophilic leukocytosis was often recorded in the general blood test, indicating the addition of bacterial flora.

Conclusions. It should be summarized that the analysis of clinical symptoms of various stages of CKD indicates that the disease remains unattended for a long time and may not have any clinical symptoms. Starting from 3B, most patients began to note increased pressure, edema. The complex mechanism of the formation of hypertension and edematous syndrome indicated the already formed pathogenetic onset of the disease. Expressed hypertension syndrome was recorded in 100 (66.2%) of the examined patients, and, accordingly, edematous syndrome in 67 (44.3%) patients, which was aggravated by hot climatic conditions and peculiarities of water-salt metabolism. Consequently, the death of nephrons indirectly leads to hyperfunction of the remaining ones. The resulting hypertrophy of nephrons leads to hypertrophy of the entire organ, and the patient may not have clinical symptoms for a long time. In this regard, many authors call such adaptive capabilities of the kidneys "bad", since they gradually lead to kidney sclerosis.

REFERENCES

1. Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) CKD Work Group. KDIGO 2012 Clinical Practice Guideline for the Evaluation and Management of Chronic Kidney Disease // *Kidney International*. –2013. –№3. –P.150.
2. See E.J. Long-term risk of adverse outcomes after acute kidney injury: a systematic review and meta-analysis of cohort studies using consensus definitions of exposure / E.J. See, K. Jayasinghe, N. Glassford et al. // *Kidney International*. –2019. –№95 (1). –P.160–172.
3. Major R.W. Cardiovascular disease risk factors in chronic kidney disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis / R.W. Major, M.R.I. Cheng, R.A. Grant et al. // –2018. – №13 (3).
4. Bogdanova A.R., Sigitova O.N., Kim T.Yu. Chronic kidney disease in outpatient practice. Study guide. Kazan: 2022.
5. KDIGO Practical Guidelines for the Diagnosis, Prevention, and Treatment of Mineral and Bone Disorders in Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD-MBD). Summary of Guidelines // *Nephrology*. 2011. Vol. 15, N. 1. Pp. 88–95.
6. Smirnov A.V., Yesayan A.M., Kayukov I.G. Chronic kidney disease: towards a unified understanding // *Nephrology*. 2002. Vol. 6, N. 4. Pp. 11–17.
7. Chronic kidney disease. Study guide. Kazan Federal University, 2024.
8. Younes S, Mourad N, Safwan J, Dabbous M, Rahal M, Al Nabulsi M, Sakr F. Chronic kidney disease awareness among the general population: tool valid on and knowledge assessment in a developing country. *BMC Nephrology*. 2022;23(1):266.
9. Shanasirova, R. S., Abzalova, M. Ya., Manashova, A. R., Boltaeva, N. N., Ortikboeva, Sh. O., & Davidkhozhaeva, A. A. (2015). Possibilities of ultrasound diagnostics in extrahepatic portal hypertension in children. *Young scientist*, (16), 100-101.
10. Yusupaliyeva, G. A., Turayeva, N. N., Turebaev, B. A., & Abzalova, M. Y. (2018). The role of complex echography in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis in children. *Spirit Time*, (7), 15-17.
11. Inoyatova, F. I., Yusupalieva, G. A., ABZALOVA, M., Sultanova, L. R., & Akhmedov, E. A. (2020). Features of doppler indices in chronic hepatitis with the transition to liver cirrhosis in children. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research (09752366)*, 12(3).
12. Yusupalieva, g. a., Rashidov, z. r., Niyazov, a. n. u., & Akhmedov, e. A. (2019). Information content of multispiral computed tomography in the diagnosis of nephrotuberculosis. *Science among us*, (3), 84-90.

13. Karimov, I., & Abzalova, M. (2023). Features of Dopplerographic indicators in chronic hepatitis with transition to liver cirrhosis in children. *Scientific works of gifted youth and medicine of the XXI century*, 1(1), 93-93.
14. Rashidov, Z., Kutumov, X., Yusupalieva, G., & Manashova, A. (2017). The state of blood flow according to ultrasound angiography in renal tuberculosis. *Journal of Problems of Biology and Medicine*, (2 (94)), 76-78.
15. Yusupaliyeva, G. A., Abzalova, M. Y., Yuldashev, T. A., Sultanova, L. R., & Ulugmurodova, K. B. (2022). Innovative Ultrasound Diagnostic Technologies for Chronic Kidney Disease in Children. *Asian Pacific Journal of Environment and Cancer*, 5(S1), 15-17.
16. Yusupalieva, G. A., Abzalova, M. Y., Akhmedov, E. A., Bekimbetov, Q. N., & Turdiev, F. E. (2022). The Possibilities of Complex Echography in the Diagnosis of Acute Appendicitis in Children. *Advances in Clinical Medical Research*, 3(1), 01-04.
17. Yusupalieva, G. A., Abzalova, M. Ya., Umarova, U. A., & Turdiev, F. E. (2022). Possibilities of complex echography in the diagnosis of hypoxic-ischemic brain changes in children. *Issues of science and education*, (9 (165)), 25-34.
18. Fazylov, A. A., Vasiliev, A. Yu., Olkhova, E. B., & Yusupalieva, G. A. (2014). Ultrasound diagnostics in pediatric practice.
19. Yusupalieva, G., Abzalova, M., Yuldashev, T., & Sultanova, L. (2023). Dopplerography in diagnostics of chronic kidney disease: modern principles of teaching to students of medical universities. *Modern trends in teaching foreign languages in the 21st century*, 1(1), 105-112.
20. Abzalova, M., Sultanova, L., Umarova, U., Yuldashev, T., & Ortikboeva, S. (2023). Ultrasound examinations in the diagnosis of intraventricular cerebral hemorrhages in children. *Science and innovation*, 2(D12), 472-478.